

Elegant synthesis of some important tetrasubstituted pyrroles

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Ethyl 3-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-4-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-methylpyrrole-5-carboxylate and ethyl 3,4-diethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-methylpyrrole-5-carboxylate have been synthesised from ethyl 4-acetyl-5-oxohexanoate and ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate respectively, by an extension and modification of Knorr synthesis. Therefore, an elegant one-pot synthesis of the title pyrroles is being reported.

Tri- and tetrasubstituted pyrroles are essential starting substances for synthesis of symmetrical as well as unsymmetrical dipyrromethanes which are invaluable intermediates for the synthesis of porphyrins. Synthesis of ethyl 3-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-4-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-methylpyrrole-5-carboxylate (pyrrole-I) was reported earlier¹⁻⁵, but the present synthesis has been achieved in one step.

Results and Discussion

Previously reported synthesis^{1,2,4} of pyrrole-I involved quite tedious and lengthy synthetic steps to get a β -free pyrrole, by thermal decarboxylation followed by hazardous method of formylation using HCN/HCl and subsequent conversion of it to acrylic acid and finally esterifying hydrogenated acrylic acid. Clezy *et al.*^{3,5} also could not do away the lengthy route except an improvement of reagent used.

In the present synthesis, the tedious step of decarboxylation as well as the hazardous step of formylation are eliminated to give the pyrrole-I in one step (Scheme 1) by

reductive condensation of α -nitrosodiethylacetonedicarboxylate (2) and ethyl 4-acetyl-5-oxohexanoate (3). In the same way ethyl 3,4-diethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-methylpyrrole-5-carboxylate (pyrrole-II) was synthesised by reduction of α -nitrosodiethylacetonedicarboxylate (3a) with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid and simultaneously coupling with ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate (5a) (Scheme 2).

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were determined on a Varian A-60 instrument, relative to TMS (tetramethylsilane) as internal standard. All the solutions in water-immisible solvents were dried over sodium sulphate prior to evaporation. Tlc was carried out on silica gel G (Merck) using either chloroform or chloroform-methanol.

Ethyl 4-acetyl-5-oxohexanoate⁶, ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate⁷ and diethylacetonedicarboxylate⁸ were synthesised by reported procedures.

Pyrrole-I: An aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (12 g) in water (17 ml) was added to a solution of diethylacetonedicarboxylate⁸ (30 g) in glacial acetic acid (57 ml) with stirring at 10–15°. The mixture was stirred for 2.5 h at 25° and left overnight. The nitroso compound so obtained was added to ethyl 4-acetyl-5-oxohexanoate⁶ (30 g) in acetic acid (50 ml) with stirring followed by zinc dust (15 g) in small portions at 65–70°. After heating the reactant at 90–95° for 1.5 h it was poured into ice-water (1 dm³) with stirring. Suspension of the product was decanted from any excess of zinc and separated by filtration. It was washed with cold water, dissolved in ethanol, and water was added to produce turbidity and kept overnight, the ester being obtained as colourless needles (13 g, 26.6%), m.p. 65–66° (lit.⁴ 63–63.5°); δ (CDCl₃) 9.25 (1H, s, NH), 4.2 (2H, q,

$\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.35 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 2.55 (4H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 2.24 (3H, s, ring CH_3), 1.28 (3H, t, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.30 (3H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.31 (3H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

Pyrrole-II : Amyl nitrite (15 g) was added to a stirred and cooled mixture of diethylacetonedicarboxylate⁸ (25 g) and conc. HCl in 30 min. The nitroso compound was added slowly into stirred solution of ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate (25 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml). Zinc dust (13 g) was added in small portions at 60–65°. After stirring for 2 h at 95°, the hot solution was decanted and poured into ice-water (1 dm³). The resulting solid was washed with cold water. It was dissolved in ethanol and the insoluble portion was separated by filtration. The filtrate gave crystals from aqueous ethanol as light yellowish needles (12 g, 29.7%), m.p. 62–63°; δ (CDCl_3) 9.52 (1H, s, NH), 4.14 (2H, q, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.32 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 2.22

(3H, ring CH_3), 1.30 (3H, t, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.32–1.34 (6H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

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